

Research Article

Information Needs and Information Seeking Behavior of Students in Federal College of Agriculture Akure, Ondo State

¹Gbotoso, A.O., ^{2*}Adeeko, A., ³Salvador, M.Y and ⁴Olagoke, O.O

¹Library Department, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure. Ondo State.

²Department of Agricultural Extension and Management, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure. Ondo State.

³Library Department, Lagos State Polytechnic, Ikorodu. Lagos State.

⁴Department of Agricultural Technology, Oyo State College of Agriculture, Igboora, Oyo State. *Corresponding author: dkabiiodun@gmail.com

Abstract

The study investigated the information needs and information seeking behavior of students of Federal College of Agriculture Akure. The study ascertained the socio-economic characteristics of respondents, identified information needs and sources of information, determined the perception of respondents' information seeking behavior and identified the constraints to meeting their information needs. Data was obtained from 295 randomly selected students with the aid of a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings revealed that 84.4% of the students were between 17-25 years with mean of 20.4 years, 51.5% of the respondents earned between ₦6,000 and ₦15,000 with a mean of ₦8,798.17k, 57.3% were males, 94.9% were single, 51.9% needs information to complete academic assignment and 78.6% source for information to carry out research work, 81.6% source for information daily. Grand mean of the perception of students according to information seeking behavior was 4.19. The most significant constraint to information seeing behavior of the respondents was power outage (93.9%) had constraint of no regular electricity supply as a barrier to seeking information. Chi-Square results showed that age ($\chi^2=255.000$, $P=0.000$), monthly stipend ($\chi^2=146.219$, $P=0.000$) and Household Size ($\chi^2=41.688$, $P=0.035$ significantly influenced information needs) Sources of information was also significant with frequency of seeking information ($\chi^2=80.520$, $P=0.000$). The study concluded that information need and information seeking behavior of students is so crucial to the success of students in Federal College of Agriculture, Akure in achieving their goals. It was recommended that the library staff should modify their public relations and ensure good rapport between them and the students so as to encourage the students in seeking necessary assistance.

Keywords: Education, information needs and information seeking behavior, knowledge

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Introduction

Information is an important and powerful resource for our daily living as human beings and as a nation. We cannot do without information. It is fundamental for the generation of knowledge and the satisfaction of the multi-various document of the populace in an efficient manner. It is vital in daily life because information served as a resource for the growth and development of an individual. Therefore, it is very vital to the overall development of human beings and nations; hence we seek, receive, manage and make use of information on daily basis for us to progress, better informed and knowledgeable. Library patrons seek information because they need information resources to survive in all sectors of life (Ajiboye and Tella, 2007, Fiankor and Adams, 2004, Fatima and Ahmad (2008).

Osuala (2001) cited in Utor and Utor (2007) documented information as facts and opinions provided during the course of daily life. Tella (2009) asserted that information plays a significant role in the academic activities of learner in this digital era where information is a factor production Information has become a household commodity, especially in an educational institution, it is therefore pertinent to stress that for learners to succeed in academics, they needed to be highly informed, equipped, and relentless in the quest for the right information and utilized it wisely. According to Aina (2014), information can be needed for recreation, leisure or meeting tasks that are considered crucial to survival or information that could meet day to day activities or even information that is necessary for the common good of the neighborhood, community and the nation in general.

Ejiwoye and Ayankola (2011) showered that the essence of teaching and learning in any educational institution is to impart knowledge to students. Ajibero (1993) as cited by Ehigiator (2000) sees information as “data of value in planning, decision making, and evaluation of programme”. Also in defining information Hampshire (1991) is of the view that information is something which our senses can detect /feels either directly or with the assistance of a device. This definition is in line with the generally accepted opinion that information is anything that causes a change or alteration in the mind of an individual or group of individual. Meanwhile, academic success of students’ is measured by their performance and how they meet the standards set out by the regulatory bodies and the institution by maximizing the available information. Lin and Wang (2012) noted that the quality of information in education is an antecedence that affects continuation of learning intention through the receipt of current teaching resources and knowledge sharing with colleagues and getting notification in preparation for examination. Ogba (2013) opined that information needs vary from function to function, environment to environment, discipline to discipline and even from age to age. Uhegbu (2007) noted that information need implies a lack of something which if present would further our welfare or make easier

the attainment of whatever objectives one may have in mind. It is a state or process started when one perceives that there is a gap between the information and knowledge available to solve a problem and the actual solution of the problem (Miranda and Tarrapanoff, 2008). This however implies that lack of information needed into accomplish tasks results in information need. Their concept of information need also means the need for information whenever an individual is faced with a situation that requires knowledge to handle such situation. Therefore, information need is a gap in person's knowledge, when experienced at the conscious level as a question, gives rise to a search for an answer.

According to Safahieh (2007), information needs perform five broad functions and these functions are the fact-finding function, which provides answers to specific question, the current awareness function, which keeps information up-to-date, the research function, which investigates a new field in-depth, the briefing function, which obtains a background understanding of an issue, and the stimulus function, which provides ideas to obtain stimulus. Adelani (2002) in his study drew attention to the fact that there are spectrums of factors affecting information needs and this include age, educational level and linguistic ability of the user as well as other job related factors such as rank and length of experience, the nature of work (i.e. management, research or teaching) the subject field, the stage that a project has reached, size of the immediate work team, nature of the institution where the user works (academic or industrial), size of the institution and the communication structure within the institution. Information needs are diverse and constantly changing and not amenable to generalization.

Information seeking behaviour is a broad term, which involves a set of actions that an individual, such as undergraduates, takes to express information needs, seek information, evaluate and select information and finally uses this information to satisfy his/her information needs (Fatima and Ahmad, 2008). It is therefore described as an individual's way and manner of gathering and obtaining information for personal use, knowledge, updating and development. In other words, information seeking behaviour involves active or purposeful information as a result of the need to complete course assignment, prepare for class discussions, seminars, workshops, conferences, or write final year research paper.

Information seeking is also an essential activity in the academic environment. It is associated with every task performed in an academic area such as teaching, research and services, this activity may be actively or passively done when taking steps to satisfy a felt need (Ikoja - Odongo, (2000).

Wilson (2000) opined that information needs are influenced by a variety of factors such as the range of information sources available; the uses to which the information will be put; the background, motivation, professional orientation and individual characteristics of user. Other factors are socio-political, economic, legal and regulatory systems surrounding the users as well as the consequences of information use. There is the need to study the information seeking behavior of the students of the Federal College of Agriculture, Akure because there are low grades among the students and most students are not kept abreast of the happenings in academics and also in the larger society. There is therefore the need to study the information need and information seeking behavior of students in Federal College of Agriculture, Akure so as to contribute to the improving the overall exposure of the students and enhance their academic performance..

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. describe the social economic characteristics of the students in the study area;
- ii. identify information needs and various sources of information by students;
- iii. determine the frequencies of uses of these sources of information use by students
- iv. determine the perceptions of information seeking behavior of the students ; and
- v. identify the constraints in accessing information by the respondents.

Hypotheses of the Study

The two hypotheses of the study are stated in the null form:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between selected socio economic characteristics and the level of information needs of the respondents.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between sources of information and the level of information seeking behavior of students

Methodology

The study was carried out at the Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study area was deemed appropriate and suitable for the study because it is an institution of higher learning with students at the National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (HND) levels. The population for the study consists of all the students in the college. A list of the students studying at the College was retrieved from the College registry and the list of all the eight (8) existing Departments in Federal College of Agriculture was used. A random sampling technique was used to select thirty five (35) students from seven (7) departments while fifty-five (55) students

were selected from Animal Production Department being the most populated department making a total number of three hundred (300) students. However, 295 students responded during the course of the study. Data were obtained from the students using a well validated structured questionnaire. Validation of the questionnaire was done by expert in the field of library. Data were analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics include the use of frequency counts and percentages while the inferential Statistics used was the Chi-Square. A 5-point likert scale was used to determine the perception of respondents according to information seeking behaviour (SA-Strongly Agreed, A- Agreed, U- Undecided, D- Disagreed and SD- Strongly Disagreed). A mean score was calculated for each statement and a Grand Mean (GM) was also calculated which determined the overall perception of the respondents according to information needs and information seeking behavior in the study area. The criterion for determining the perception score stipulates that if the Grand Mean is greater than 3.0, then the students perceived the effect of information needs and information seeking behavior is real and that it is not affecting the overall academics activities of the students. If the Grand Mean score is less than 3.0, then the students do not perceived the effect of information needs and information seeking behavior and that it is affecting the overall academic activities of the students. The hypothesis for this study was subjected to inferential statistics i.e Chi-square. This helps to determine if there is a significant relationship between the students' perception and information seeking behavior of the students.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 revealed the socio-economic characteristics of the students, findings showed that majority (84.4%) of the students were between the age of 17 and 25 years. The mean age of the students was 20.4 years. As expected, the result showed that the respondents were young. Findings also showed that slightly above half (51.5%) of the respondents earned monthly stipend of between ₦6,000 and ₦15,000, some (43.5%) of the respondents earned monthly stipend of less than ₦5,000 and only 2.3% and 1.6% of the respondents earned monthly stipends of above ₦30,000 and between ₦16,000 and 30,000 respectively. The mean monthly stipend was ₦8,798.17k. Monthly stipends for students could influence the students negatively in their quests for seeking information and the information needed by such student. If a student received limited monthly stipend (pocket money), he might not be encouraged to look for the necessary information he needed in fulfilling his academic obligation in school otherwise they will be looking for other means to fulfill their financial obligations. About 57.3% of the respondents were males while 42.7% of the respondents were females. The gender distribution is a clear indication that both male and female genders were well involved in the study. Findings also showed that majority (94.4%) of the respondents were single, very few (4.7%) of the respondents were married and only (0.3%) of the respondents were separated. The overall results of the socio economic characteristics

of the respondents could one way or the other affect students information need and information seeking behavior in the study area. This was confirmed by the findings of Okonoko *et al.*, (2015) who opined that some socio economic factors affect information needs and information seeking behavior such as age, educational level, nature and linguistic ability of the users (students).

Table 2 revealed the information needs of the respondents and the sources of information available to students. About 51.9% of the respondents noted that they sought information in order to carry out specific academic assignments given to them by their lecturers. This implied that students would need to visit the library often and make use of other electronic facilities like personal computer systems, e-library to access both hard copies of journals and books or soft copies or online journals to complete their academic assignments Also, text books, lecture notes can be frequently consulted, this is in line with the findings of Owolabi *et al.* (2010) who found that students use information primarily for academic purpose. This finding also agrees with the findings of Oyadeyi (2014) who concluded that exposure of students to assignments, examinations, seminars and workshops have played a key role among the factors that influences information seeking behavior of undergraduate students. Findings also showed that 78.3% of the respondents use previous research work as a source of academic information. The implication of this is that in carrying out assignments by students, they need to visit previous students' research work for guidance, procedures and corroboration of previous research findings.

Table 3 revealed the frequency of seeking information by the respondents. Findings showed that 81.7% of the respondents sought information on a daily basis. This implied that since academic activities takes place on a daily basis, students will always be kept on their toes to seek for information to advance their academic career. This is in line with the findings of Oyadeyi (2014) who documented that students visit library daily to borrow books related to their subjects, reading novels and for other academic purpose.

Table 4 revealed the perception of respondents according to their information seeking behavior. Findings revealed on the overall that students' perception about information needs and seeking behavior was very high; this was further revealed in the Grand Mean (GM) score of 4.16 of the perception statements the respondents. This Grand Mean score of 4.16 is an indication that respondents perceived that information seeking behavior is helping the students in academic performance. This further implied that students used information primarily for academic purpose, to network with others, for good grade, to pass examinations, to contribute to the society, to pass professional exams, to develop their personal life and to enrich their knowledge.

Findings on Table 5 showed the various constraints encountered by students in seeking information. These constraints were ranked to determine the most felt constraints. No regular power supply ranked 1st (93.9%), high cost of data and unavailability of internet facilities ranked 2nd (89.2%) and outdated library resources ranked 4th (87.1%) and these were the major constraints affecting students in their quest for seeking information. Other constraints includes; short duration of library opening hour (86.8%), non-conducive learning environment (82.7%), inadequate awareness of information resources (85.8%), inaccessibility of information resources (85.1%), low quality of information resource (85.4%), bad attitude of library personnel (52.2%), insufficient time to seek for information (86.4%) and lack of comfortable library facilities (86.1%). These findings have been supported by LittleJohn and Benson-Talley (1990) who confirmed that student's limitations in borrowing, insufficient number of books, outdated materials, poor users of educated programs were to barriers limiting the students' access in information in the library. Also Omopupa and Abdulraheem (2013) study revealed that library opening hours limits undergraduates access to information and regulates the time that students can visit the library for information.

The results of the hypothesis showed that there was a significant relationship between Age ($\chi^2=255.009$), Monthly stipend ($\chi^2=146.219$) and Household size ($\chi^2=41.688$) and information needs of respondents. This result could imply that students who happened to be young and energetic could seek and need information for their academic performance. Findings also showed that there is a significant relationship between sources of information and the level of information seeking behavior of students ($\chi^2=80.520$), this could imply that if sources of information is easily available, it could influence the information seeking behavior and frequency of seeking information by the respondents.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents According to Socio Economic Characteristics (n=295)

Socio Economic Characteristics	Frequency (%)	Mean Score
Age (Years)		
Less than 16 years	16 (5.4)	20 .4
Between 17 - 25 years	249 (84.4)	
Between 26 - 35 years	29 (9.8)	
Above 35 years	1 (0.4)	
Monthly Stipend		
Less than ₦5,000	127 (43.5)	₦8,798.17k
Between ₦6,000- ₦15,000	153 (51.9)	
Between ₦16,000 -₦30,000	5 (1.6)	
Above ₦30,000	7 (2.3)	
Household Size		
Less than 5 persons	222(75.3)	5.0
Between 6- 19 persons	72 (24.4)	
Above 10 persons	1 (0.3)	
Sex		
Male	169 (57.3)	
Female	129 (42.7)	
Marital Status		
Single	280 (94.4)	
Married	14 (4.7)	
Separated	1 (0.3)	

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 2: Distribution of Respondent According to Information Need (n=295)

	Frequency (%)	Mean Score
Information needs of the respondents		
Research	83(28.1)	
Assignment	153(51.9)	
Project	57 (19.3)	
Others	2 (0.7)	
Source of Information		
Friends	15 (5.1)	
Library	9 (3.1)	
Internet	39 (13.2)	
Research Work	231(78.3)	

Source: Field Survey. 2019

Table 3: Distribution of Respondent According to Frequency of Information Source (n=295)

Frequency of Information Source	Frequency (%)
Daily	241(81.7)
Every other day	8(2.7)
Weekly	28(9.5)
Fortnightly	8(2.7)
Monthly	10(3.4)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 4: Perception of Respondent According to Information Seeking Behavior (N=295)

Perception Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean Score
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	
1. I seek information for better performance	205(69.5)	89(30.2)	1(.3)	1(.3)	–	4.68
2. I seek information to network with others	187(63.4)	103(34.9)	1(.3)	4(1.4)	–	4.60
3. I seek information to get more exposed to happenings around me	200(67.8)	91(30.8)	3(1.0)	1(.3)	–	4.66
4 I seek information to improve my research skills in academic activities	201(68.1)	91(30.8)	2(.7)	1(.3)	–	4.66
5 I seek information to contribute my quota to the development of the school	140(47.5)	146(49.5)	4(1.4)	4(1.4)	–	4.42
6 I seek information for professional examinations	96(32.5)	46(15.6)	14(4.7)	29(9.8)	110(37.3)	2.91
7 I seek information to develop my personal life	143(48.5)	149(50.5)	3(1.0)	–	–	2.65
8 I seek information to enrich my knowledge	227(76.9)	68(23.1)	–	–	–	4.76

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Note: SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, U= Undecided, D= Disagreed, SD= Strongly Disagreed

Table 5: Constraints to seeking Information by students (N = 295)

Constraints Encountered	Yes	No	Ranking
1 High cost of internet data	263(89.2)	31(10.5)	2 nd
2 Irregular electricity supply	277(93.9)	17(5.7)	1 st
3 Out dated or obsolete library resources	257(87.1)	37(12.5)	4 th
4 Short duration of library opening hour	253(86.8)	42(14.2)	5 th
5 Unavailability of internet facilities	263(89.2)	32(10.9)	2 nd
6 Unfavorable environment (Noise)	244(82.7)	51(17.3)	11 th
7 Inadequate awareness of information Resource	253(85.8)	42(14.3)	8 th
8 Inaccessibility of information Resources	251(85.1)	43(14.6)	10 th
9 There is no quality of Information Resources	252(85.4)	42(14.3)	9 th
10 Bad attitude of library personnel	154(52.2)	141(47.8)	12 th
11 Insufficient time to seek information	255(86.4)	37(13.6)	6 th
12 Lack of comfortable library facilities	254(86.1)	41(13.9)	7 th

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Result of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between selected socio economic characteristics and information need of students.

Table 6: Chi Square Result of Socioeconomic characteristics and information need of Students

Relationship	χ^2 Calculated	df	P- Value	Decision
Age	255.009	51	0.000	S.
Sex	5.819	3	0.121	NS.
Marital Status	7.659	6	0,264	NS.
Monthly Stipends	146.219	66	0.000	S.
Household Size	41.688	27	0.035	S.

Significant @ 0.05 S = Significant NS = Not Significant

Hypothesis 2

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between sources of information and information seeking behavior of students

Table 6: Chi Square Relationship between Sources of Information and Information Seeking Behaviour of Students

Relationship	χ^2 Calculated	df	P-value	Decision
Source of information	80.520	16	0.000*	S

Significant @ 0.05 S= significant NS= Not Significant

Conclusion

The study has shown that age, household size and monthly stipends of the students had significant relationship with information needs. It was revealed that there was a significant relationship between sources of information and information seeking behavior of the students. Information need and information seeking behavior of students is so crucial to the success of students in tertiary institution in achieving their goals.

Recommendations

The study recommended the following:

- i. The library staff should organize user education/workshop at the beginning of every semester or session for all categories of students. The workshop should focus more on the use of academic database and other electronic information resources; and
- ii. The library staff should also modify their public relations and ensure good rapport between them and the students so as to encourage the students in seeking necessary assistance.
- iii. The College should make internet service a must and easily available and affordable for the students with constant electricity on the campus, this will encourage information seeking behavior of students thereby impact positively on their academic performance.

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